

AppendixTabel 2
Nilai Akhir Mata Kuliah Akuntansi Jasa Dagang

No	Nilai Akhir	No	Nilai Akhir	No	Nilai Akhir	No	Nilai Akhir	No	Nilai Akhir	No	Nilai Akhir
1	75.7	26	85.5	51	83.65	76	83.1	101	75.8	126	51
2	78.8	27	91	52	80.05	77	59.4	102	86.8	127	78.65
3	85.7	28	83.3	53	76.95	78	75.6	103	75.8	128	63.8
4	84.9	29	87.2	54	81.65	79	82.35	104	87.6	129	58.9
5	90.65	30	88.2	55	87.55	80	77.6	105	80.1	130	59
6	86.35	31	89.25	56	80.95	81	68.15	106	76.1	131	66.7
7	80.6	32	91	57	84.65	82	92.15	107	82.95	132	83.65
8	90.6	33	84.55	58	86.25	83	84.75	108	83.4	133	49.8
9	85.6	34	84.2	59	80.65	84	80.85	109	85.9	134	67.3
10	85.4	35	77	60	79.05	85	74.05	110	83.1	135	48.75
11	88	36	86.35	61	84.6	86	81.1	111	83	136	55.15
12	86.2	37	81.1	62	75.05	87	0	112	81.9	137	78.95
13	76.9	38	80.8	63	84.6	88	88.05	113	90.1	138	53.1
14	88.3	39	82.08	64	83.6	89	50.3	114	90.4	139	64.85
15	86.05	40	81.7	65	79.7	90	87.9	115	78.2	140	71.75
16	84.8	41	72.85	66	74.38	91	89.9	116	90.3	141	65.4
17	85.6	42	81.58	67	86.1	92	87.4	117	89.6	142	63.75
18	87.4	43	80.15	68	75.5	93	90.35	118	81.9	143	65.55
19	83.4	44	74.35	69	42.8	94	85.8	119	89.4	144	67.5
20	75.3	45	83.1	70	83.75	95	86.4	120	71	145	58.1
21	88.5 A	46	81.15	71	86.3	96	74	121	90.8	146	74.25
22	82.2	47	80.5	72	62.85	97	81.6	122	77.7	147	48.05
23	90.65	48	83.9	73	85.85	98	79.2	123	72.45		
24	79.5	49	87.5	74	69.4	99	78.7	124	69.3		
25	85.7	50	85.4	75	69.25	100	81.3	125	85.45		

Tabel 3
 Nilai Akhir Mata Kuliah Pengantar Akuntansi 1

No	Nilai Akhir	No	Nilai Akhir	No	Nilai Akhir	No	Nilai Akhir	No	Nilai Akhir	No	Nilai Akhir
1	82.95	31	77.87	61	70.9	91	85.2	121	54.3	151	46.65
2	77.98	32	85	62	52.5	92	77.8	122	53.01	152	71
3	76.42	33	59.75	63	81.5	93	81.3	123	47.68	153	59.4
4	82	34	85.05	64	0	94	85.4	124	82.75	154	79.75
5	74.9	35	85	65	75	95	82.8	125	86.7	155	63.8
6	82.52	36	79.45	66	81.5	96	90.4	126	85	156	68.75
7	78.52	37	70.1	67	65.1	97	88.95	127	73.62	157	5.25
8	85.45	38	67.95	68	78.7	98	82.2	128	73.64	158	80.5
9	69.95	39	80.7	69	0	99	82.05	129	60.01	159	0
10	80.45	40	0	70	82.95	100	75.65	130	70.94	160	74.4
11	83.4	41	63.45	71	69.95	101	81.6	131	72.74	161	75.75
12	85.4	42	63.4	72	81.55	102	75.3	132	70.35	162	64.75
13	78.48	43	84.25	73	56.35	103	76.65	133	80	163	74.75
14	69.4	44	70.1	74	65.35	104	88.9	134	82.74	164	85.65
15	83.35	45	71.8	75	86	105	68.45	135	92.3	165	10
16	69.7	46	84.35	76	76.55	106	86.25	136	70.07	166	51.45
17	82.68	47	64.55	77	80.2	107	82.2	137	85.54	167	55.6
18	75.85	48	73	78	80.6	108	55.4	138	87.8	168	84.1
19	80.55	49	69.9	79	85.7	109	65.5	139	94.78	169	88.7
20	86.3	50	85.05	80	0	110	80.1	140	93.74	170	6.8
21	73	51	65.65	81	83.75	111	55.85	141	71.35	171	70.65
22	64.9	52	69.35	82	82.9	112	57.75	142	68.88	172	51.1
23	85.95	53	0	83	78.1	113	66.5	143	80.18	173	82.8
24	67.9	54	65.05	84	75.4	114	65.6	144	73.9	174	80.05
25	80.25	55	85.2	85	87.5	115	55.2	145	60.11	175	80.25
26	81.58	56	82.8	86	73	116	55.5	146	80	176	75
27	85.25	57	83.4	87	71.35	117	10.9	147	85.73	177	68.4
28	85.03	58	80.1	88	0	118	83.85	148	73.79	178	59.7
29	83.92	59	69.2	89	89.2	119	70.85	149	46.7	179	56.4
30	76.93	60	60.05	90	89.35	120	81.65	150	55.45	180	48.7
										181	71.55